

Research Article

Change Detection of Land Use/Land Cover by Using Remote Sensing and GIS

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Abstract Land use and land cover is an important component in understanding the interactions of the human activities with the environment and Land evaluation purpose, thus its necessary to be able to simulate changes. The Present paper attempted the change detection of land use during 1989 to 2015 on the basis of Remote Sensing data and GIS Software with the help of ArcGIS10.2, ERDAS 2011 Software and Remote Sensing Data. The base map Land use and land Cover is prepared with the help of Landsat 5 TM in year 1989 and Landsat 8 year 2015. It is found that considerable change in land use and land covers have been detected during 1989 to 2015 on the Landsat Imagery. The present study of land use on a micro scale natural region of meso watershed like Waghur Basin. Amongst various parameters of the land uses following five classes have been considered in this study. Land under agriculture, Land under forest, Land under Built-up area, bare land and Land under water bodies. The result of the work shows a rapid growth in Water bodies, Settlement and Agriculture land while rapid decrease in forest and bare land between 1989 and 2015.

1. Introduction

With increasing population pressure on the land, the land utilization on land use has acquired a special significance in various populous countries including India since; past studies have made to assess the various aspects of land use to correlate with the agricultural crops with a view to increasing the productivity of the land to its maximum capacity (Singh, 1967). Land use and land cover (LULC) change is a major issue of global environment change. Scientific research community called for substantive study of land use changes during the 1972 Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment, and again 20 years later at the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED). At the same time, International Geosphere and Biosphere Programme (IGBP) and International human Dimension Programme (IHDP) co-organized a working group to set up research agenda and promote research activity for LULC changes. Land use / land cover mapping is essential component where in other parameters are integrated on the requirement basis to drive various developmental index for land and water resource. Land use refers to man's activities and the varied uses which are carried on over land and land cover refers to natural vegetation, water bodies, rock/soil, artificial cover and others noticed on the land (NRSA, 1989). Land Cover defined as the assemblage of biotic and a biotic component on the earth's surface is one of the most crucial properties of the earth system. Land cover is that which covers the surface of the earth and land use describes how the land cover is modified. Land cover includes: water, snow, grassland, forest and bare Soil. Land Use includes agricultural land, builtup land, recreation area, wildlife management area etc. In this study to map out the status of land use land cover of Waghur Basin between 1989 and 2015 with a view to detecting the land use change. Remote Sensing data is very useful because of its synoptic view, repetitive coverage and real time data acquisition. The digital data in form of Landsat satellite imageries, therefore, enable to accurately compute various land cover / land use categories and helps in maintaining the spatial data infrastructure (SDI) which is very essential for monitoring urban expansion and change detections studies (Lo, 1981; Mukherjee, 1987; and Quarmbly & Cushine, 1989). In other words, the remote sensing satellite data in multi-resolution and multispectral means to provide spatial information for land

cover / land use at different levels for various aspects as built-up land, agricultural land, forests, wastelands and water bodies etc. So, the land cover / land use maps prepared using multi-date and multispectral data provides different levels of spatial information which are used in change detection studies (Burrough, 1986). The present study on a meso scale watershed like Waghur Basin it extends between 20° 27' 32" to 21° 05'43" N latitude and 74° 30' 7" to 76 ° 05' 11 " E longitudes. Amongst various parameters of the LULC following five classes have been considered in this study. Land under agriculture, Land under forest, Land under Built-up area, bare land and Land under water bodies.

2. Methods and Material

The aim of this paper is to detect the Land use / Land cover change from 1989 to 2015. The multi-spectral satellite data is used for supervised classification for prepare Land use map. The software ERDAS-9.2 and ArcGIS 9.3.1 is used for data processing. The data utilized is given in the following tables for the years 1989 and 2015. The Geographic Information System (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) tools have been applied to find out the land cover / land use changes over periods in the Waghur basin. Such as the ArcGIS and ERDAS have been used for geographical analysis, integration, and presentation of the spatial and non-spatial data for land cover / land use change detection. So, these tools are more effective for monitoring and modeling for land cover / land use changes.

Table 1: Data Source and Acquisition (Remote Sensing data)

RS data	Date	Band
Landsat 5	Oct 1989	2,3,4
Landsat 8	Oct 2015	3,4,5

Figure 1: Methodology Flow Chart

3. Results and Discussion

The Land use maps of Waghur basin for both the years reveal five classes of Land use. Viz Land under agriculture, Land under forest, Land under Built-up area, bare land and Land under water bodies. The classified images obtained after preprocessing and supervised classification which are showing the land use and land cover of the Waghur basin are given in the following figure 2 & 3. These images provide the information about the land use pattern of the study area.

Table 2: Spatio-Temporal distribution of Land use of Waghur basin

LULC	Year 1989 Area (sq.km)	Area in %	Year 2015 Area (sq.km)	Area in %
Forest Land	310.71	12.50	283.82	11.42
Agriculture Land	987.45	39.74	1389.13	55.90
Bare Land	1152.5	46.38	744.5	29.96
Settlement	19.30	0.78	35.26	1.42
Water Bodies	15.04	0.61	32.29	1.30
Total Area	2485.00	100	2485.00	100

Figure 2: Land use/ Land cover map of Waghur basin 1989

Table 3: Land use Change Detection during 1989 – 2015

LULC	Year 1989 Area (sq.km)	Year 2015 Area(sq.km)	Increase Area(sq.km)	Decrease Area(sq.km)
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Forest Land	310.71	283.82	26.89
Agriculture Land	987.45	1389.13	401.68
Bare Land	1152.50	744.50	408.00
Settlement	19.30	35.26	15.96
Water Bodies	15.04	32.29	17.25
Total Area	2485.00	2485.00	

Figure 3: Land use/ Land Cover Map of Waghur basin 2015

4. Conclusion

This research work demonstrates the ability of GIS and Remote Sensing in capturing spatial-temporal data. Attempt was made to capture as accurate as possible five land use classes as they change through time. The five classes were distinctly produced for each study year but with more emphasis on Settlement and Agriculture land as it is a combination of anthropogenic activities that make up this class; and indeed, it is one that affects the other classes. However, the result of the work shows a rapid growth in Water bodies (17.25 km^2), Settlement (15.96 km^2) and Agriculture land (401.68 km^2) while rapid decrease in forest (26.89 km^2) and bare land (408 km^2) between 1989 and 2015. Above finding gives potential for land evaluation of Waghur basin.

Figure 4: Land use/ Land Cover Change Detection Map

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